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D.5.1 Profiling-for-memory-and-streaming-hardware

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Glossary

3G	3rd Generation
ACP	Accelerator Coherency Port
AHB	AMBA High-performance Bus
ALU	Aritmetic Logic Unit
AMBA	Advanced Microcontroller Bus Architecture
AP	All Programmable
APB	Advanced Peripheral Bus
ARM	Advanced Risc Machine
ASB	Advanced System Bus
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
ATB	AMBA Trace Bus
BRAM	Block RAM
CABA	Cycle Accurate Bit Accurate
CAT	Communication Architecture Tuner
CCM	Code Coverage Metrics
CE	Computing Elements
CL	Configurable Logic System
CLSM	CPU Load and Status Metrics
COT	Completion On Time
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRAFTERS	ConstRaint and Application driven Framework for Tailoring Embedded Real-time Systems
DAP	Debug Access Port
DDR	Double Data Rate
DMA	Direct Memory Access
DRAM	Dynamic Random Access Memory
DSE	Design Space Exploration
DSP	Digital Signal Processing
ET	External timestamping of trace data that is presented via an external interface
ETB	Embedded Trace Buffer
ETM	Execution Time Metrics
FIFO	First In First Out
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
FSL	Fast Simplex Link
FTM	Fabric Trace Monitor
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDL	Hardware Description Language
HDMI	High-Definition Multimedia Interface
HI	Hardware instruction trace
HT	Hardware branch trace

HTML	HyperText Markup Language
HW	Hardware
HWCM	HW Communication Metrics
IC	Inter Integrated Circuit
I/O	Input/Output
IP	Internet Protocol
IP	Intellectual Property
IRQ	Interrupt Request
ISR	Interrupt Service Routine
IT	Internal timestamping of trace data via on-chip mechanisms
ITLM	ISR and Task Latency Metrics
ITM	Instrumentation Trace Macrocel
LAN	Local Area Network
LMB	Local Memory Bus
MEM	Memory Exploitation Metrics
MPI	Message Passing Interface
OLED	Organic Light-Emitting Diode
OS	Operating System
PAU	Performance Analysis Unit
PC	Personal Computer
PDF	Portable Document Format
PLB	Processor Local Bus
PMTS	Performance Monitoring Tool Suite
PU	Processing Unit
QoS	Quality of Service
RISC	Reduced Instruction Set Computer
RMS	Rate Monotonic Scheduling
RS 232	EIA RS-232 Electronic Industries Alliance Recommended Standard 232
RTL	Register Transfer Level
RTOS	Real-Time Operating System
SC	Software-based reading of a free-running clock
SCU	Snoop Control Unit
SD	Secure Digital
SDIO	Secure Digital Input Output
SIMD	Single Instruction Multiple Data
SMP	Simmetric Multi Processor
SoC	System-on-Chip
SPI	Serial Peripheral Interface
SW	Software
SWCM	SW Communication Metrics
TA	Technical Annex
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TLM	Transaction Level Modelling
TPIU	Trace-Port Interface Units

VGA	Video Graphics Array
VHDL	VHSIC Hardware Description Language
VLNV	Vendor, Library, Name, Version
WCET	Worst Case Execution Time
Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1 Introduction

This deliverable, together with related D5.3 and D5.9, represents the main output of task T3.5.1. Such a task describe, develop and deliver *profiling techniques* (i.e. methodologies, metrics, tools and related hardware/software mechanisms) to monitor computational behavior and communication patterns of hardware/software components of multi many-core processor systems representing the CRAFTERS platform.

The main goal is to collect data from such systems and made them available for offline analysis and visualization, i.e. to be used at design or validation-time (e.g. to provide measures to validate the estimations made by timing analysis tools) or online use, i.e. integrated into silicon devices to be used at run-time (e.g. to support the dynamical resources management). Moreover, for safety critical systems, they could be used to enforce timing encapsulation and potentially provide recovery mechanisms to improve system availability under the influence of hard or soft errors and for coverage of some systemic software problems. To reach such a goals, the T5.3.1 deliverables content have been organized as follows (as described in the Technical Annex):

- **D5.1: Profiling for memory and streaming hardware**
 - *This deliverable describes profiling techniques for memory behaviour and streaming hardware*
- **D5.3: Profiling for communication and resource usage**
 - *This deliverable describes profiling techniques with a special focus on system communication and resource usage*
- **D5.9: Profiling for network-on-chip systems**
 - *This deliverable describes profiling techniques for network-on-chip and systems-on-chip solutions*

However, as a result of a preliminary analysis of requirements and deliverables related to D5.1 (i.e. D2.1 and D4.1), it has been realized the need of early shared opinions to some relevant issues. In particular, considering T3.5.1 deliverables:

- What does it means "streaming hardware", considering CRAFTERS target final platform (namely a many-core/multi-processor system)?
- What are the actual differences between the T3.5.1 deliverables? Is "communication" related also to "streaming hardware"? Does "resource usage" applies to all the deliverables?

The first shared opinion has been that T3.5.1 deliverables overlap a lot. So, partners agreed on consider them in an incremental manner. In particular, they deal with similar metrics and mechanisms but, while D5.1 focuses on component-level metrics (i.e. profiling of one component or very few components with reduced interactions), D5.3 focuses on platform-level metrics (i.e. profiling of complete basic HW/OS platforms, maybe similar to those used in the use cases, with a lot of interacting components), and D5.9 focuses on network-on-chip and systems-on-chip solutions while considering also applicative aspects related to use cases implementations.

The second shared opinion has been that the “deliverable nature” specified in the TA (i.e. *Report, Prototype, Demonstrator, Other*) was not properly set for T3.5.1 deliverables. In particular, the prototype nature of D5.1 has been considered inappropriate and the following modification has been agreed:

- D5.1: **report** instead of prototype
- D5.3: **prototype** instead of demo
- D5.9: **demo** instead of prototype

So, this deliverable provides the first results of task T3.5.1 while describing platforms, metrics, and preliminary integration/design activities of tools and HW/SW mechanisms to be used to monitor computational behavior and communication patterns of hardware/software components. In particular, it focuses on **memory behavior** and **streaming hardware** (i.e. the hardware components involved in streaming operations) at component-level grain (i.e. profiling of one component or very few components with reduced interactions) while, as said before, the following T3.5.1 deliverables will focus on platform-level and system-level issues also providing working prototypes and a final demo.

The specific contributions of involved partners to T3.5.1 deliverables are detailed below:

- UAQ/TIT: description of platforms that will be used in D5.3 (and possibly in the TIT case study) to develop and validate prototypes; definition of the proposed metrics (related to memory access and bus arbitration); preliminary design of the hardware mechanisms that will be specifically developed for the CRAFTERS project as prototypes in D5.3/D5.9 and used to perform profiling in the TIT case study
- BUT/CAMEA: development of a performance profiling library. The library will collect and preprocess data for later analysis. Statistics displaying tool will be based on existing CAMEA solution, which will be improved in the context of the CRAFTERS project. The library and the application will be used in collaboration with CAMEA for profiling of traffic monitoring systems.
- BBT: description of QUAD [QUAD_2013] software profiler together with the generated metrics. The QUAD tool will be then extended in the context of CRAFTERS project to multi-threaded execution and, if feasible, to evaluate metrics considering also temporal aspects.
- RPT: development of a lean and cost-efficient tracing systems for multi-core platforms. Previous experience from the MERASA project [MERASA_2013] will be applied to collect timed execution traces for execution time measurements. Moreover, RPT will investigate profiling solutions for the *Infineon TriCore* architecture and technology [TRICORE_2013].
- ALT: contributions to metrics definition and exploitation of OpenComRTOS [GW_2013]. Such a RTOS will be extended in the context of CRAFTERS project to exploit WP5 results.
- MDS: exploitation of the IP-XACT standard for abstract platform representation and design space exploration in the context of the CRAFTERS project.

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- IFX-UK: collaboration with UK SME RPT (and other interested partners) by providing TriCore platform to perform research activities in the context of the CRAFTERS project. The goal is be to define techniques and measure that could be integrated into silicon devices used in safety critical systems.
- ULB: contributions to metrics definition and exploitation of HIPPEROS [HIPPEROS_2013]. Such an RTOS will be extended in the context of the CRAFTERS project to exploit WP5 results.

While this Section has clarified scope and goals of the deliverable as well as roles and contributions of partners, the rest of the document is organized as follow:

- Section 2 describes the target platforms selected by the different partners to develop and validate future prototypes and the components, belonging to them, that will be profiled;
- Section 3 defines the metrics that will be evaluated by means of profiling data;
- Section 4 describes profiling methodologies and provides preliminary design of tools and HW/SW mechanisms that will be developed/integrated in CRAFTERS and eventually used to perform such a profiling;
- Section 5 describes a standard notation that could be used in the context of the CRAFTERS project to provide a unified view of the information provided in the previous sections;
- Section 6 draws out some conclusions and define the future work mainly related to the content of next T3.5.1 deliverables.

The document has been internally reviewed by Vihavainen Kari (CC) and Vlad-Mihai Sima (BBT).

2 Target Platforms and Components

This section describes the target platforms selected by the different partners to develop and validate prototypes and the *fuse* (i.e. *hardwired*) or *soft* hardware components, belonging to them, that will be profiled. Such components are classified in *Processing units*, *Storage systems* and *Interconnections*.

2.1 Heterogeneous Multi Many-Core Processor Systems based on ARM and FPGA platforms (BUT, CAMEA, UAQ, TIT)

2.1.1 Platforms

The platforms considered by BUT, CAMEA, UAQ and TIT in T3.5.1 task belong to the category of “Heterogeneous Multi Many-Core Processor Systems”. In particular, they consider those systems based on ARM platforms, FPGA platforms and their combinations. They are composed of several processor units interconnected in one or more chips. Nowadays ARM+FPGA or ARM+GPU cooperation is quite common. Appropriately distributed algorithm between processor units leads to improved performance of the whole system. A novel way of integration CPU cores and FPGA is to embed both technologies into one chip.

The goal is to exploit such platforms to design and validate profiling tools and/or HW/SW mechanisms by deploying developed ones over a target “multi many-core platform”. More in detail, the target platforms are based on the *Xilinx Zynq-7000* configurable SoC [Zynq7000_2013], a good example of useful combination of ARM processor and FPGA chip and, in particular, UAQ/TIT will use the *ZedBoard* [ZedBoard_2013] development kit. So, this section firstly describes the main features of selected platform and related SoC and then provides more details about processing units, storage system and buses that will be used during the design and validation phases while highlighting some profiling related features to be considered during the development phase.

2.1.1.1 Xilinx Zynq-7000

Xilinx Zynq-7000 (Figure 1) is a family of configurable system on chip, each one including an hardwired ARM based processing unit (PU) and a configurable logic system (CL) based on FPGA technology. Xilinx Zynq-7000 is able to satisfy the needs of a wide range of applications (Automotive driver assistance, Industrial motor control, industrial networking, and machine vision, LTE radio and baseband, Medical diagnostics and imaging). Each device in the Zynq-7000 family contains the same PU, an ARM Cortex A9 dual-core processor system, while configurable logic and I/O resources vary between the devices.

Those devices offer the flexibility and scalability of FPGA technology, particularly useful for custom logic development purposes. Moreover, they provide a tightly integrated dual core processor, easily allowing the implementation of an heterogeneous many core platform (e.g. a system in which the hardwired processor cooperates with one or more soft processors implemented in FPGA fabric). The integration of the PU with the CL

allows the development of solutions that two-chip configuration cannot match due to their limited I/O bandwidth, latency, and power budgets.

Xilinx ISE Design Suite development environment fully support Zynq 7000 software and hardware development. A large number of peripheral devices are provided as soft IP cores for the implementation on programmable logic subsystem. Stand-alone and Linux device drivers are available both for the PU hardwired peripherals than CL based cores. Moreover, ARM-based PU allows the use a broad range of third-party tools and IP.

The inclusion of an application processor enables high-level operating system support, e.g., Linux (other standard operating systems for the ARM Cortex A9 are also available for the Zynq-7000 family).

Figure 1 - Xilinx Zynq 7000 All Programmable SoC Schematization

2.1.1.1.1 ZedBoard

The ZedBoard is a development board based on the Xilinx Zynq-7000 Configurable SoC. ZedBoard includes Xilinx XC7Z020-1CLG484CES Zynq-7000 AP SoC, flanked on 512 MB DDR3 (128M x 32) and 256 Mb QSPI Flash memories. Zynq 7000 supports HDMI and VGA (12 bit Color) display. ZedBoard also features a 128x32 OLED display. ZedBoard is fully supported in Xilinx ISE Design Suite.

2.1.2 Processing Units

A processing unit (PU) is a complex sequential engine executing algorithms expressed by a machine code. They are designated to run most of algorithms, such as scientific computing, graphics, network and database applications etc. On the other hand, overall

attributes (performance, power consumption, size, cost, etc.) of application could be deficient. One of the purposes of profiling is finding the location of application or architecture bottlenecks. Basic parts of common PU are the arithmetic logic unit (ALU), cache memory, control unit and I/O controller.

Since Xilinx Zynq 7000 SoC natively offers an hard-wired (i.e. *fused*) dual core ARM Cortex M9 processor, tightly coupled with an FPGA fabric on which soft and custom processor can be implemented, these kind of processing units will be described in the following.

2.1.2.1 ARM CPU

ARM processors become popular in small embedded systems. They have a RISC instruction set, and newer core families are partially backward compatible. RISC means, that only basic instructions are supported, which fact leads to small processor complexity. Both the ARM architecture and instruction set are configurable. This leads to small, effective processor with low power requirements. That's why their popularity is still rising, especially in embedded and mobile segment. ARM processors are sold by ARM holding as a design file, not as physical chip. In this respect, they are quite similar to IP cores for FPGAs. Hence manufacturers can build their own chips with custom peripherals based on ARM processor core. Considering profiling information while working with these kind of processors is very important since it is possible to obtain valuable information about hardware demands. Algorithms can be redesigned to fit the architecture parameters (e.g. cache memory size, or individual core utilization, etc). ARM core can also be generated and manufactured for exact application, which can save resources, such as battery power in embedded devices. Because platforms based on ARM processors are capable to run UNIX-like operating systems, application profiling could be quite simple using system profiling tools. In practice, two different tools are widely used. Gprof [GPROF_2013] is a profiling tool based on instrumenting the target program with additional instructions. They are determined to obtain calling information, such as number of function calls. Actual timing information (e.g. execution time) are obtained by statistical sampling. Instrumenting the program can cause program performance changes, potentially causing inaccurate results or time-depending bugs. Sysprof [SYSPROF_2013] profiler gathers only statistical information about an application. A sampling profiler probes the target program's counter at regular intervals using operating system interrupts. Sampling profilers are usually less accurate, but allow the target application to run almost at full speed and they do not have any side-effects on program execution.

2.1.2.1.1 ARM Cortex A9 (hardwired)

The Cortex-A9 MPCore (Figure 2) is a 32-bit multi-core processor developed and licensed by ARM Holdings Ltd. It relies on a configurable architecture providing up to 4 cache-coherent Cortex-A9 cores, each implementing the ARM v7 instruction set architecture. Cortex A9 cores are natively arranged for multi-processing operation support. Each core has an out-of-order speculative issue superscalar execution pipeline with optional NEON SIMD instruction set extension (which allows up to 16 operations per instruction). Each core supports the execution of 32 bit ARM instruction set, Thumb-2 (16 bit) instruction set

CRAFTERS – ConstRaint and Application driven Framework for Tailoring Embedded Real-time Systems and Jazelle technology [JAZELLE_2013] for direct Java bytecode execution. The application processing unit of Xilinx Zynq 7000 contains two ARM Cortex A9 cores.

Figure 2 - Zynq 7000 Processing Unit Schematization

Processors share 512 KB L2 cache while each one implements two separate 32 KB L1 caches for instruction and data. The *Snoop Control Unit* (SCU) is responsible for maintaining L1 cache coherency between the two processors and the ACP interface from the CL. A 256 KB on-chip memory module parallel to L2 cache acts as low-latency memory. Debug and trace capability is built into the two processor cores and interconnects as a part of the CoreSight [CORESIGHT_2013] debug and trace system. The user can control and interrogate both processors and the memory through the debug access port (DAP). Furthermore, 32-bit AMBA [APB_2003] trace bus (ATB) masters from the two processors are funneled with other ATB masters, such as *Instrumentation Trace Macrocell* (ITM) and *Fabric Trace Monitor* (FTM), to generate the unified PU trace through the on-chip embedded trace buffer (ETB) or the trace-port interface units (TPIU).

2.1.2.2 Soft-core CPU

Soft core processors are processors typically described by a HDL language. *PicoBlaze* and *MicroBlaze* by Xilinx [XILINX_2013] are typical representatives of such soft core processors. They are commonly used in complex FPGA designs such as controllers for

acceleration and peripheral units, but they are not intended to directly execute complex computing algorithms. Very compact size and easy use are main benefits of this solution. Processing units like *Pico/Micro-Blaze* are made to be as simple and customizable as possible. Main memory is often connected externally to the core, so there is a possibility to connect profiling circuit for analyzing memory as well as analyzing the soft core itself. Soft cores synthesized in the FPGAs are typically smaller and less powerful than the traditional CPUs and their main purpose is typically hardware/software co-design, control functions, or compatibility/legacy software exploitations. The possibilities of profiling are very similar to the general CPUs (e.g. the above mentioned ARM cores). In addition, however, results of profiling can be used for optimizing the soft core itself, e.g. through gathering information about exploitation of application specific instructions, registers, or interfaces.

Two soft processor devices have been considered in detail: proprietary Xilinx MicroBlaze [MicroBlaze_2007], natively supported by Xilinx Design Environment, and LEON 3 core [GRLIB_2013], included in Aeroflex-Gaisler open-source GRLIB IP library.

2.1.2.2.1 MicroBlaze

MicroBlaze (Figure 3) is a proprietary soft processor core (i.e. a processor core entirely implementable in FPGA logic and general purpose memory) specifically designed for Xilinx FPGAs from Xilinx. MicroBlaze has a 32 bit RISC architecture with instruction and data cache, pipeline with branch prediction and low latency interrupt mode.

Figure 3 - MicroBlaze Processor Schematization

The majority of MicroBlaze features are user selectable and configurable: cache size, pipeline depth (3-stage or 5-stage, respectively for area or performance optimization), optional memory management unit, optional barrel shifter, hardware multiplier, divider and floating point unit, number and type of bus-interfaces.

MicroBlaze interconnection system is based on IBM CoreConnect [CORECONNECT_2013] bus specification and proprietary bus solutions. Specifically, PLB, a synchronous multi-master bus PLB is the main system bus and represents the preferred bus for third-party high performance IP interfacing. OPB (on chip peripheral bus) is a secondary synchronous multi-master bus for slower devices interconnection. LMB (local memory bus) is the bus provided by Xilinx for local memory (FPGA on chip block RAM) interconnection. A fast, unidirectional, FIFO-style bus, the FSL (Fast Simplex Link) is Xilinx native solution for co-processor and hardware accelerators interfacing. Moreover, newer version of MicroBlaze also supports AXI bus, which is part of ARM AMBA specification.

MicroBlaze allows the use of operating systems requiring hardware-based paging and protection (like the Linux kernel) with the addition of the optional Memory Management Unit. Otherwise, embedded operating systems like FreeRTOS or uCLinux are fully supported.

2.1.2.2.2 Leon3

LEON is a 32-bit CPU core series based on SPARC-V8 RISC architecture and instruction set. Originally designed by the European Space Agency (LEON and LEON 2 models), it has been successively developed and distributed by Gaisler Research (LEON 3 and LEON 4 processors). A LEON processor is fully described in synthesizable VHDL and can be implemented in programmable logic (such as an FPGA) or manufactured into an ASIC.

Figure 4 - AeroflexGaisler Leon 3 Processor Schematization

LEON3 (Figure 4) includes Symmetric Multi-Processing (SMP) support and a seven-stage pipeline. Processor features are fully configurable through VHDL generics.

LEON 3 is part of the GRLIB, an HDL part library containing a large number of LEON 3 compatible IP cores. The GRLIB full source code is available both under an LGPL/GPL FLOSS license (www.gnu.org) and a proprietary license, respectively for non-commercial applications and commercial use and distribution.

2.1.2.3 *Custom PU*

FPGA chips offer an opportunity to design custom processing units instead of using existing ones. Standard processor architectures are largely fixed, general, and easily reprogrammable only by changing an application source code. In case of FPGAs, an algorithm is directly part of a circuit design and can't be so easily modified. Custom hardware enables easy parallel computing unit setup. This allows creating very powerful computing units for specific algorithms and optimal resource utilization as well. On the other hand, developing and debugging of custom designs is extremely time-consuming. Profiling information can provide information about the resource utilization of each element of a design. With such statistics, the design can be optimized for example by sharing or resizing some design elements. Alternatively, circuit clock frequency could be decreased. Both way of optimization leads to power and chip space savings. As for the profiling, the custom CPUs are very similar to the soft core ones except for even higher focus on use for optimization of resource exploitation and application specific instructions, etc.

At the moment no custom PU usage is planned in this deliverable apart from the HW mechanisms and components that will be specifically developed for profiling purposes as output of T3.5.1 task.

2.1.3 Storage Systems

The storage systems serve for preserving of the data being processed, constants, code of the program (machine code), etc. The basic parameters of the storage systems include the type, capacity, throughput, latency, and the ability to store the data when the power is disconnected. The required memory size is one of the most important features of the algorithms. Additionally, the features of the memory can significantly affect the performance, power consumption and also price of the systems. The memory can be further subdivided into on-chip and off-chip. The following sections provide more details and considerations about memories while describing also the actual components related to the selected platform and development board.

2.1.3.1 *On-chip Memory*

Processing units require a storage memory to run applications. In order to meet full potential performance of the PU, this memory has to be as fast as the PU. Technically it is possible to produce such fast memory, but with extreme resource consumption. Hence memory is divided into hierarchy by speed/size ratio and on chip itself is located small and resource expensive memories to be used as caches or as special-purpose tightly-coupled memory. Cache memory is further hierarchically divided into several levels, L1, L2 and eventually L3 by their latency/size ratio. L1 is fastest, but quite small, only for immediate result and instruction caching. Cache searching is partially associative. Partial associativity has a great disadvantage that an arbitrary memory block can be cached only in predetermined cache cells. This solution can cause a performance decrease, when random memory blocks are accessed, because cache is often flushed. In this case, current PU's have greater associative level (2,4 or 8-way) that reduces cache flushing. Cache profiling can bring valuable information about cache utilization, such as cache filling and

hit/miss ratio. Software can be optimized in that way, for example to improve memory access coalescing which leads to higher cache hit ratio. For embedded segment, cache utilization statistics can be useful when selecting suitable platform CPU. Generally, FPGA chips do not have fixed cache memory line in CPU. Custom registers and cache memory could be distributed all over the circuit, just where are needed. Distributed storage is resource expensive, thus BRAM blocks can be used for larger memory blocks.

2.1.3.2 *Main Memory*

Main memory commonly consists of random access dynamic memory modules (DRAM). It is used to store currently running programs code and their data. Most relevant parameters are memory size and latency. Latency of DRAM modules is large in general (around 50us and more), thus relatively small processor cache is used to hold copy of processed data. So, memory access statistics can be used to track down application memory accesses, which can provide a base for program optimization process. Uncoalesced or highly random memory access can cause often cache flushing and thus repeatable DRAM read/write cycles. Typical examples are matrix operations calculated over columns. Program dynamic memory requirements are observable by operating system tools. Relevant statistics are useful in optimization process or during embedded system development.

2.1.3.3 *Extended Memory*

Computer hard disk, Flash disk or SD card are typical representatives of extended memories. These devices latencies are from hundreds of microseconds (flash memories) to several milliseconds (classic hard disk). Operating system performs data transfers from extended memory to main memory transparently to user application. Memory access profiling is then directly part of the operating system, which holds statistics of I/O operations for every process. For example, *iostat* is one of the Linux utilities for displaying I/O memory statistics.

2.1.3.4 *Zynq 7000 SoC and ZedBoard Memories*

Zynq 7000 SoC memory hierarchy includes a 32 KB Level 1 set-associative instruction and data caches (independent for each CPU), and a 512 KB set-associative Level 2 cache (shared between the CPUs). Zynq PU contains a hardened memory interface unit, including a dynamic memory controller and static memory interface modules.

The ZedBoard includes two Micron MT41J128M16HA-15E:D DDR3 memory components creating a 32-bit interface. The ZedBoard features a 4-bit SPI (quad-SPI) serial NOR flash (Spansion S25FL256S) used to provide non-volatile code, and data storage. It can be used to initialize the PU subsystem as well as configure the PL subsystem (bitstream). The Zynq PU SD/SDIO peripheral controls communication with the ZedBoard SD Card (A 4GB Class 4 card is included in the ZedBoard kit.) The SD card can be used for non-volatile external memory storage as well as booting the Zynq-7000 AP SoC. Configurable logic subsystem includes 36 Kb of True Dual-Port Block RAM.

2.1.4 Interconnections

Various types of interconnection exist. In particular, the following sections focus on *buses* and *peripherals device buses*. The structures of interest include specifically the mechanisms for data transfer in the embedded system with functionality split between fixed functionality CPU and programmable hardware, such as Xilinx Zynq 7000.

2.1.4.1 AMBA BUS

The Advanced Microcontroller Bus Architecture (AMBA [AHB_2006]) specification has been selected as preferred bus architecture for many core target platform implementations and is widely used on SoC designs. On Xilinx Zynq 7000 platform, FPGA part and ARM processor are interconnected through AXI bus, which is part of the AMBA specification. Custom peripherals implemented in FPGA are directly connected to this bus, having also bus master ability with direct DDR memory access. This section summarizes AMBA architecture main features and highlights main profiling action challenges.

AMBA is a registered trademark of ARM Holdings and is an open (de facto) standard for embedded microcontrollers communication and SoC peripheral interconnect. First version of AMBA specification was introduced by ARM Ltd in 1996 and included Advanced System Bus (ASB) and Advanced Peripheral Bus (APB). The second version, AMBA 2, introduced AMBA High-performance Bus (AHB). AHB and APB buses are still the fundamental building blocks of AMBA based architectures and a de-facto standard for processor interconnection. The third version of the specification, AMBA 3, introduced AXI bus to reach even higher performance interconnect and the Advanced Trace Bus (ATB) as part of the *CoreSight* [CORESIGHT_2013] on-chip debug and trace solution. In 2010 the AMBA 4 specifications were introduced starting with AMBA 4 AXI4, then in 2011 extending system wide coherency with AMBA 4 ACE.

The AHB bus [AHB_2006] is specifically designed for high-performance, high speed module interconnection within a system on chip. Intended as high-performance backbone bus, AHB supports an efficient connection of processors, on-chip memories and off-chip external memory interfaces. AHB bus protocol has the following features:

- single clock edge protocol: a clock cycle is defined from rising edge to rising edge transition of the clock signal;
- split Transfers: a slave can signal to the bus arbiter that a data transfer could require a large number of clock cycles issuing a dedicated SPLIT signal. Bus arbiter can then prevent master bus access until the transfer is complete. This separation between master addressing and slave data transfer allows a better bus utilization;
- multiple bus masters: several bus master can coexist on the same bus;
- burst transfers: AHB bus supports burst data transfers. A master starting a transaction can explicitly signal a burst data transfer;
- pipelined operations: bus operations are pipelined, e.g. the bus performs arbitration for the next transfer during the current transfer;
- single-cycle bus master handover: in case of multiple bus master, the handover phase between two different master requires a single clock cycle.

A simple transaction on the AHB consists of an address phase and a subsequent data phase (Figure 5). In case of multiple master devices, a MUX prevents conflicts allowing a single master access at time. For a bus with a single master AMBA specification also includes AHB-Lite, which is a simplified version of AHB.

Figure 5 - AMBA AHB Bus Writing and Reading Cycles

APB [APB_2003] is a bus designed for low bandwidth control accesses (for example register interfaces on system peripherals) and explicitly intended for low-power peripherals interconnection. This bus (Figure 6) has an address and data phase similar to AHB, but a much reduced, low complexity signal list.

Figure 6 - AMBA APB Bus Writing and Reading cycles

AXI bus [AXI_2004] is the third generation of AMBA interface and is targeted at high performance, high clock frequency system designs. Its features make it very suitable for high speed interconnect:

- separate address/control and data phases: address and control signals issuing are separated from actual data transfer phase, allowing overlapped burst transfers;
- burst based transactions: AXI protocol support burst write and read transaction; only start the address of the bus is provided, while successive burst address are derived from the control signals;
- support for unaligned data transfers: AXI protocol uses burst-based addressing, but allows to begin a transfer from an unaligned address;

- issuing of multiple outstanding addresses: masters can issue transaction addresses without waiting for earlier transactions to complete, allowing parallel processing of transactions;
- out of order transactions: transactions to faster memory regions can be completed without waiting for earlier transactions to slower memory regions, thus reducing transaction latency effects.

Due to the relevance of such a standard, there already exists a direct debugging and profiling support from Xilinx in form of IP cores to be connected to AXI bus. They can easily gather transfer statistics, limited range signal waveforms and display them on host PC just like at oscilloscope. Profiling info about AXI bus traffic is useful for communication scheduling, especially in real-time systems, where latency is critical.

2.1.4.2 *Peripheral Interfaces*

LAN, Wi-fi or 3G are widely used peripheral data interfaces not only on personal computers, but even more on embedded segment. Traffic profiling of such peripherals is often included as a part of operating system or TCP/IP stack library. Beside software profiling tools, HW packet sniffer for network monitoring are applicable. Additionally, more traditional interfaces, such as serial links (UART, RS 232, SPI, I²C, etc...), and proprietary parallel interfaces are of interest.

2.2 *Other multi-core systems in T3.5.1*

IFX-UK will provide TriCore architecture and technology to UK SME RPT (and other interested partners) to perform research activities in the context of the CRAFTERS project. In particular, topics of main interest will be:

- hardware profiling mechanisms;
- cache coherency and hit rate;
- data lifetime;
- process timing;
- memory encapsulation mechanisms.

The goal is to define techniques and measures that could be integrated into silicon devices used in safety critical systems. Such mechanisms are aimed to provide:

- design time measures to validate the estimations made by timing analysis tools;
- run-time mechanisms to enforce timing encapsulation;
- recovery mechanisms to improve system availability under the influence of hard or soft errors and for coverage of some systemic software problems.

3 Metrics

This section describes the metrics that will be evaluated in the CRAFTERS project by means of profiling. For each metric are provided, when applicable, profiling motivations and expected goals (e.g. optimization of specific software regions, consumptions reduction, bug detection etc.), possible profiling requirements (e.g. accuracy, real-time issues etc.), and current available solutions (commercial or research solution, with specific bibliographical references). However, it is worth noting that the metrics listed in the following are not to be considered exhaustive since new ones could be added later (i.e. in next T3.5.1 deliverables) depending on the needs of the project (i.e. requirements and case studies) not clearly defined at this time.

3.1 Memory Exploitation Metrics (MEM)

Memory exploitation metrics are mainly related to runtime memory usage analysis and they allow to characterize systems behavior and to better define systems architecture. The metrics related to memory exploitation that will be available in the CRAFTERS platform are the following:

- MEM#1 (UAQ/TIT)
 - Access statistics for on chip and off chip memory devices: number of read and write operations in a given period of time for a specified memory area (i.e. a single memory location or a whole address range) of a specified memory
- MEM#2 (UAQ/TIT)
 - Elapsed time between two sequential specified memory accesses (i.e. write-write, write-read, read-write, read-read) on a specified memory location
- MEM#3 (UAQ/TIT)
 - Cache memory statistics: total number of cache hit and miss in a given period of time for a specified cache memory

3.1.1 Profiling motivation and expected goals

Profiling of the memory exploitation is one of the key means of understanding the exploitation of the memory subsystem which is one of the key factors in efficient exploitation of the computer system (single and/or multi-core). Moreover, the monitoring of the memory exploitation over the time can help improve performance and can help in achieving better balance of individual threads.

With respect to the target platforms and components described in Section 2, such metrics have been proposed by UAQ since Xilinx does not provide profiling IP core for MicroBlaze based systems, excepted the AXI bus Performance Monitor. Aeroflex Gaisler provides some profiling IP Core (for example, the Leon 4 Statistics Unit [GRLIB 2013]), but none of these comes with the open source version of the library.

3.1.2 Profiling requirements

The requirements for profiling include hardware means, such as counters, implemented in individual piece of hardware or (in the proposed cases) in programmable hardware, such as FPGA. The collected data is then processed in software.

The following general requirements can be listed:

- Passive monitoring
 - Designed resources have to collect, store, and output data to a central coordination unit. No modification of the processing system dynamic behavior tailored by the profiling sub-system is provided.
- Non-intrusive profiling
 - The main goal of profiling mechanisms design will be the minimization of introduced overhead on software execution time. Possible disadvantages in terms of power consumption or area occupation should be tolerable and, as far as possible, reduced.
- Heterogeneous multi-processor architectures support
 - Designed mechanisms will natively support the extension for multi-core operatio
- Portability
 - Designed mechanisms have to guarantee an high level of portability towards different bus architectures.

3.1.3 Current available solutions

Memory profiling mechanisms can be based on software techniques or rely on direct hardware support.

3.1.3.1 *Software based solutions*

Software based solution usually follows the general approach of classic profiling tools, like *Valgrind* [VALGRIND_2013] with the tools *cachegrind* and *massif*. Instrumentation of source code allows to generate interrupts and sample the program counter [Varley_1993], obtaining various statistics about software execution. Software profiling necessarily introduces some overhead on execution time, and has some grade of statistical inaccuracy (essentially due to the sampling approach). Current CPUs have a direct hardware support to memory access profiling. It provides the information about the kernel and executables on the system, such as when memory is referenced, the number of L2 cache requests, and the number of hardware interrupts received. On Linux system, the utility *OProfile* [OPROFILE_2013] uses this hardware to collect samples of performance-related data each time a counter generates an interrupt. If monitoring hardware is not present, timer-based substitute solution is used instead. These information are periodically written to disk. Later, these samples are processed into performance reports that can be used to improve system and application performance.

3.1.3.2 *Hardware based solutions*

Hardware profilers are instead based on dedicated hardware resource able to carry on the profiling action. This means that no source code instrumentation is needed and software execution by the central processor unit is not altered, thus no overhead on execution time is introduced. For the same reason, hardware solutions can guarantee best accuracy of performance analysis. However, hardware based solutions require a larger silicon area occupation for system implementation. Other possible disadvantages are the difficulty to correlate low level measurements to source code performance metrics and the limited number of allocable hardware resource, that often forces the developer to collect desired performance metrics by means of multiple tests. Various examples of hardware based profiling mechanisms have been presented in literature. SnoopP [Shannon_2004] and Airwolf [Tong_2008] are two function-level profilers for software application running on softcore processors. SnoopP contains a user-specified variable number of segment counters, used to measure the number of clock cycles spent in executing of contiguous regions of memory. Each segment contains two comparators to check the value of the program counter between the specified low and high address. If the value of the PC is presently accessing an address within these bounds, then the counter value is incremented. Airwolf is used to calculate the run-time of each function by counting the number of system clock cycles. Airwolf does not require instrumentation code, although some extra code (needed to activate and deactivate a particular profiling counter) is added to each function. Airwolf contains 20 profiling counters which allow for up to 20 functions to be profiled at a time. Processor manufacturers usually include performance monitoring units in their products. For example, Intel Pentium 3 and AMD Athlon processors provide a set of hardware performance counters. Embedded processors and SoC (e.g. ARM based solutions like ARM Cortex A8 and ARM Cortex A9) often allow the inclusion of profiling resources as a design option.

3.2 *HW Communication Metrics (HWCM)*

HW communication metrics are mainly related to bus analysis: runtime analysis of bus arbiter units (i.e. the units designed to coordinate communication on system buses) allows to characterize system global dynamic behavior and to better distribute available resources. The metrics related to communications by HW components (i.e. PUs) that will be available in the CRAFTERS platform are the following:

- HWCM#1 (UAQ/TIT)
 - Transaction count: number of transactions occurring during a specified monitoring period over a monitored bus (also called SWitching activity)
- HWCM#2 (UAQ/TIT)
 - Data size: total size of data transferred over a monitored bus during a specified monitoring period
- HWCM#3 (UAQ/TIT)
 - Data transfer time: amount of time required for burst data transfer, expressed in number of clock cycles

- HWCM#4 (UAQ/TIT)
 - Transaction time: total amount of time required for a single transaction execution.
- HWCM#5 (UAQ/TIT)
 - Transaction latency: time required from address generation to the first service of data in a single bus transaction, expressed in number of clock cycles

3.2.1 Profiling motivation and expected goals

The design of single processor systems (i.e. systems including a single master processor core on a shared communication bus) is usually based on the calculation of required bandwidth for each system component. On the basis of this quantitative analysis, system designer can choose the appropriate bus architecture and correctly allocate resources. In case of multi-processor systems (i.e. systems including multiple processor chips on a single board), single processor design is complemented by a board level inter-processor communication analysis, usually based on the use of logic analyzers. These approaches are not feasible in the case of modern multi-processor system on chip. Bandwidth allocation methodology is complicated in the case of multiple-bus (or bus network based) complex multiprocessor system. Moreover, the main goal of communication analysis is debugging, as the limited time scope of the observation does not allow a full system performance characterization and when multiple core are integrated on a single die, internal signal are not available for probing. A detailed analysis of system on chip dynamic behavior is fundamental to correctly allocate available resources and to exploit intrinsic SoC parallelism. The inclusion of on-chip appropriate profiling resources becomes thus essential. The design of a novel inter-processor communication profiling unit is necessary, since Xilinx does not provide profiling IP core for its native bus solutions systems, excepted the AXI bus Performance Monitor. Aeroflex Gaisler provides some communication profiling IP Core (for example, the Leon 4 Statistics Unit [GRLIB 2013]), but none of these comes with the open source version of the library.

3.2.2 Profiling requirements

The following general requirements can be listed:

- Passive monitoring
 - Designed resources have to collect, store, and output data to a central coordination unit. No modification of processing system dynamic behavior tailored by the profiling sub-system is provided.
- Non-intrusive profiling
 - The main goal of profiling mechanisms design will be the minimization of introduced overhead on software execution time. Possible disadvantages in terms of power consumption or area occupation should be tolerable and, as far as possible, reduced.
- Transaction oriented monitoring action
 - Design mechanisms will be primarily targeted to the analysis of bus transaction
- Heterogeneous Multi-Processor Support for system level profiling

- Designed mechanisms will natively support the extension for multi-core operation
- Portability
 - Designed mechanisms have to guarantee an high level of portability towards different bus architectures

3.2.3 Current available solutions

Profiling of HW components communications (i.e. PUs) can be based on the use of software tools or directly rely on hardware support.

3.2.3.1 *Software based solutions*

Software based solutions are based on the use of specific software components able to sample inter-core message passing activity. Vetter [Vetter 2002] proposed PHOTON, a software profiling tool able to track message passing activity by means of additional profiling relevant information added to the passed messages. PHOTON includes an MPI profiling layer that implements message sampling and a custom MPI runtime that appends profiling information to individual message. Chang et al. [Chang 2012] designed a Performance Monitoring Tool Suite (PMTS), a software solution capable of analyzing bus utilization/contentions for the specific case of 3D graphics SoC application.

3.2.3.2 *Hardware based solutions*

Many commercial system-on-chip solutions natively offer dedicated communication profile resource, usually based on communication bus sampling technique. Different bus profilers have been presented in literature. Owl [Schulz_2005] is a hardware based profiler for reconfigurable hardware based systems. The tool allows to monitor communication between processing elements in a multiprocessor system and is based on hardware counters directly synthesized in FPGA along with target cores. WOoDSTOCK (Watches Over Data Streaming On Computing element linKs) [Shannon2_2004] is a real-time system profiler designed for reconfigurable hardware based platform. It is used to monitor the data flow between Computing Elements (CE) connected by Xilinx Fast Simplex Link bus. Measuring the number of run-time execution clock cycles, the tool is able to determine if a CE is stalled or starved for data. Kiung et al. [Kyung 2010] proposed a Performance Analysis Unit (PAU) which targets AMBA AXI bus. PAU supports bus latency measurement, bus traffic measurement and specific durations bus utilization characterization. The core also allows the profiling of contention between master/slave devices. Communication Architecture Tuner (CAT) [Lahiri 2004] is instead a so-called “active monitor” able to configure the on-chip communication protocol parameters dynamically (e.g., priorities, burst modes, etc.). CAT offers great control power and flexibility, but has a strong dependency on target application (i.e. its logic should be modified if target applications changes).

There are also examples of commercial bus specific solution. IBM provides an hardware counting unit (PLB performance monitor) able to measure the number of events associated with CoreConnect PLB bus-transactions. ARM provides a hardware macro-cell (AHB Trace Macrocell) able to collect data trace information about the AHB buses. Xilinx recently introduced a profiler for the supported AXI bus.

3.3 SW Communication Metrics (SWCM)

Software communication metrics are metrics that will be collected at high level, without involving any specific platform. The metrics related to communications by SW parts that will be available in the CRAFTERS platform are the following:

- SWCM#1 (BBT)
 - Number of bytes/addresses/unique data values that are produced and consumed by pairs of functions (or, if needed and feasible from a performance perspective, between other, smaller granularity, parts of the application)
 - Such a metric will be considered also from a temporal point of view, if other constraints (for example execution time overhead) allows this
- SWCM#2 (BBT)
 - Data access patterns within functions. The complexity of the patterns identified is subject to investigations of the complexity of the implementation
 - An example of such pattern are the stride on which a read/write operation is performed
- SWCM#3 (BBT)
 - Data access patterns between functions (feasibility subject to ongoing investigation) from a temporal point of view. This will take the form of an ordering of the accesses to the memory blocks. The ordering should be able to highlight which memory blocks need to reside at the same time in memory, and which can be evicted sooner.

3.3.1 Profiling motivation and expected goals

Traditionally the primary objective of hardware/software partitioning on heterogeneous systems is to improve the execution performance. In order to achieve this goal, the program is profiled and the parts with higher execution time contributions are mapped to processing elements that can execute them more efficiently, while the parts with lower contributions are executed on the general-purpose processor. Nevertheless, another important aspect to be taken into consideration is the memory utilization between components. Not having profiling data related to data components might result in having a memory bottleneck, which will degrade the overall system performance.

3.3.2 Profiling requirements

The following general requirements can be listed:

- Provide a level of performance comparable to not-profiled application execution.
- Allow the user to hint the profiling tool in order to improve performance
- Obtain a level of accuracy that allows optimizations based on the obtained results

3.3.3 Current available solutions

As the motivation is to provide developers with insight into the data communication within an application, we will focus here on the available solutions that report data communication and dependence analysis. The current solutions are:

- Pincomm [Heirman_2010] is a Pin [Luk_2005] based tool that reports communication flow between various parts of the program. The parts can be data structures, functions, etc. The communication is provided as producer-consumer relationships. Compared to Pincomm, QUAD will provide an adaptive profiling granularity and profiling data storage management. This means that it will be able to faster profile functions without affecting the accuracy. It will also provide a more clear view on the memory access patterns that will help to improve the mapping of the application to heterogeneous processing elements.
- Redux [Nethercote_2003] is a Valgrind based tool for constructing detailed dynamic dataflow graph for applications. Because of the level of detail it can be used only for very small programs. Compared to QUAD, it does not focus on providing communication behavior, but its focus is to represent the computation history of a program.

3.4 Execution Time Metrics (ETM)

Execution time metrics are useful for analysis and prediction of program behavior in time. It is also important during optimization for performance bottleneck identification and rectification. The metrics related to execution time that will be available in the CRAFTERS platform are the following:

- ETM#1 (RPT, BUT/CAMEA)
 - This metric records the amount of time spent executing specific segments of code on a specific core
 - It excludes time spent executing other threads or interrupts on the same core, but do include time that could be attributed to the code, such as delays due to caching or other hardware arbitration issues
- ETM#2 (RPT, BUT/CAMEA)
 - This metric records the time statistics of function calls/interrupts handled: it specifies how many times/ how often the certain code is executed within the specified time period

3.4.1 Profiling motivation and expected goals

Execution time metric is needed for following purposes:

- evaluate execution time of specific functions;
- evaluate execution time of a single cycle of periodic tasks;
- evaluate execution time of task segments between scheduling points;
- time stamping events;
- evaluate reaction time to events (interrupts or software events);

- evaluate CPU time per task;
- workload measurement (often by measuring the application idle time).

The collection of this metric is always approximate for following reasons:

- the measurements, unless using non-intrusive hardware support, are intrusive and modify the execution behavior;
- the execution times depend on the memory architecture, placement in memory, caching policies. Hence the execution time has a probabilistic profile (histogram);
- the execution times are application and system configuration specific;
- the execution times can be influenced by external hardware.

A major issue is that the classical *Worst Case Execution Times* (WCET) are no longer usable measures as advanced architectures result in a very wide probabilistic spread. Nevertheless, the WCET even when empirically measured rather than obtained by analysis and simulation, is still a good first order approximation. By adapting a programming model that can absorb outliers (e.g. by using asynchronous interactions and time-outs) and the right caching policy, predictable real-time applications are possible. The first order WCET estimates are still needed for determining task priorities for RMS (*Rate Monotonic Scheduling*), but must be repeated with typical values (e.g. 99% probability, mean values). Execution times are increasingly insufficient to determine if an application will be time predictable and offer a sufficient *Quality of Service* (QoS). The reason is that on highly integrated advanced SoCs, the processor cores share many on-chip resources like bandwidth, memory, peripherals, DMA engines, co-processors, memory and energy. Often, the application is not able to use all the available resources or risks generating starvation for other tasks. Hence resource counters in the hardware (to be less intrusive) are needed to complement execution time measurements and software based monitors (that are intrusive). Note that an additional complexity comes from dynamic Voltage and Frequency scaling to reduce energy consumption as this modifies the hardware timings.

3.4.2 Profiling requirements

The following general requirements can be listed:

- it must be possible to identify the duration that a core takes to execute a given sequence of instructions (i.e. relative timing);
- it should be possible to record duration of instructions using a cycle-accurate clock, synchronized to the execution of the instructions;
- if a synchronized, cycle accurate clock is not available, it must be possible to record duration of instructions using a clock running at or above the speed of the CPU clock;
- it must be possible to identify which core the instructions are executed on;
- it should be possible to identify the time at which specific instructions are executed relative to some initial time (i.e. absolute timing);
- it should be possible to relate timings made on different cores;

- it may be possible to profile execution timings non-intrusively (e.g. record location of executed instruction and timestamp via hardware mechanisms that don't affect execution time);
- it should be possible to retrieve execution profiling data while the application is running, without affecting the timing behavior of the application;
- if non-intrusive execution time profiling is not possible, it should be possible to log execution times using intrusive measures that have a fixed execution time;
- if fixed-execution time intrusive profiling is not possible, it must be possible to log execution times using intrusive measures that have a bounded (and low) execution time;
- it must be possible to identify points at which context switches and interrupts take place;
- it should be hardware based to limit the intrusion and software overhead;
- it should be based on dedicated buffers that can be read out from the software or using a JTAG debugger;
- it should be based on cycle accurate instruction set simulators, including concurrent use of peripherals.

3.4.3 Current available solutions

Current software based solution usually follows the general approach of classic profiling tools, like Gprof [GPROF_2013], the GNU statistical profiler able to count the number of times functions have been called and calculate the execution time for each function. Instrumentation of source code allows to generate interrupts and sample the program counter [Varley_1993], obtaining various statistics about software execution. Software profiling necessarily introduces some overhead on execution time, and has some grade of statistical inaccuracy (essentially due to the sampling approach).

3.5 CPU Load and Status Metrics (CLSM)

Collecting of these statistics is quite common in every operating system. Load and status statistics can be used for better system optimization, identifying system weaknesses (slow CPU, memory bandwidth), etc. The metrics related to CPU load and status that will be available in the CRAFTERS platform are the following:

- CLSM#1 (BUT/CAMEA)
 - Percentage of CPU utilization: typically a log or a graph of overall CPU load over time
- CLSM#2 (BUT/CAMEA)
 - Granularity and timing of CPU utilization: this metric considers the CPU load distribution over time. The resulting statistics show in what time and how long was CPU working and when was idle
- CLSM#3 (BUT/CAMEA)

- The CPU status individual changes over the time: this metric is important for optimization of system power consumption/CPU load scheduling. Output is a graph or a log of CPU performance states over time
- CLSM#4 (BUT/CAMEA)
 - The CPU status statistics: It's a percentage expression of metric CLSM#3 over long period, specifying how long was CPU in individual performance states

3.5.1 Profiling motivation and expected goals

Profiling of the CPU status can be a key to e.g. cutting down the power consumption. In the multi-core system, individual threads can be reallocated in order to maximize power savings achieved by entering to power saving/idle mode. Moreover, the monitoring of status can help to improve performance of the CPU through better synchronization of individual threads. This knowledge can be used to effective algorithm distribution amongst individual CPU cores. In case of idle states, some computation tasks can be reallocated between CPU cores. It can lead to better utilization and higher application performance. It is, in general, necessary to find time critical parts of software and optimize them.

3.5.2 Profiling requirements

The required generated output is couple of (<timestamp>,<status>), where the <timestamp> should be unique number (probably 64-bit) identifying time of the event and <status> shall be status information containing information about the states of the CPU (it can even be concatenation of several states information). If every change of state is impossible to collect, the information should contain “summary” information about the states in a current period of time (since last timestamp) that would enable evaluation of the statistical metrics (e.g. average and standard deviation of times, etc.)

The profiling should be hardware based wherever possible. It is assumed that every change in the status of the CPU will be recorded into a memory structure, and eventually ideally into a file structure.

The profiling overhead, in this case, should be in terms of “extra hardware” as software collection of the state changes is not feasible for this resource. The “extra hardware” would most probably mean simple circuit for data collection and a BlockRAM inside some FPGA (or, perhaps, some external memory).

Other requirements can be minor software modifications and allocation of memory (CPU memory space or possibly external hardware memory). Alternatively exploitation of compiler intermediate files for localization of code and data in the profiling tools.

3.5.3 Current available solutions

Currently, a large set of profiling tools is supported by desktop operating systems. CPU Load profilers are divided into two main categories, with or without compiler assist. First way is more precise, because profiling counters and probes are inserted directly inside program code. Disadvantage is noticeable performance decrease and possibility of causing or avoiding of time dependent errors. Profilers without compiler assist use

sampling instruction pointer register of running code in regular time intervals. Results are not so accurate like in compiler assist profiling, but they are safer and easier to use, because they doesn't need the program recompilation. *Sysprof* [SYSPROF_2013] is Linux best known performance profiling utility. Windows based systems have for example *Xperf* [XPERF_2013] utility. In case of custom FPGA designs, hardware probes are quite easy to use. Profiling counters can be manually placed wherever is needed. Only problem can be gathering their information. For this purpose, well known profiling tool *Xilinx Chipscope* [CHIPSCOPE_2013] is suitable. FPGA IP core have to be connected into current design onto monitored signals/busses. Together with Xilinx Chipscope utility on PC, it arranges a connection over USB cable, for example. Collected data are then displayed on PC in the form of time diagrams. Among CPU status profilers belongs the Linux *Powertop* [POWERTOP_2013] utility. Its original focus was on CPU sleep states, and showing the programs or drivers responsible for wakeups which prevent CPUs entering sleep states. A database of known problems provides more user friendly tips for specific sources of wakeups. However, it also shows information on CPU frequency scaling. Over time the database has been expanded to include tips on a wide range of power consumption issues.

3.6 Code Coverage Metrics (CCM)

Code coverage metrics are required to demonstrate that specific sections of code have been executed (i.e. covered) by a specific set of runs. The metrics related to code coverage that will be available in the CRAFTERS platform are the following:

- CCM#1 (RPT)
 - Percentage of instruction covered by a set of runs
- CCM#2 (RPT)
 - References to section of codes not covered by a set of runs

3.6.1 Profiling motivation and expected goals

Code coverage metrics demonstrate that specific sections of code have been executed. They are required in the case of high-integrity systems to demonstrate that testing has been effective.

3.6.2 Profiling requirements

The following general requirements can be listed:

- it must be possible to identify that specific sections of code have been executed within the context of a given test;
- it must be possible to identify that specific sections of code have been executed on a specific core.

3.7 ISR and Task Latency Metrics (ITLM)

Interrupt latency is a classical measurement for real-time systems. At the application level it measures how fast a system can handle external events (i.e. hardware events). It is

determined by the application profile as well as by the way the hardware is designed and as well as how the software layer is developed. We examine this more in detail below. The metrics that will be available in the CRAFTERS platform are the following:

- ITLM#1 (ALT)
 - IRQ to ISR latency: time interval between the hardware event and the first useful instruction in the ISR
 - Such measurements could be repeated for different cache settings (target specific)
- ITLM#2 (ALT)
 - IRQ to task latency: time interval between the hardware event and the first useful instruction in a waiting task
 - Such measurements could be repeated for different cache settings (target specific)

3.7.1 Profiling motivation and expected goals

Interrupt latency is governed by the time it takes for the application running on a processor to react to typically an external event. Such an external event is typically a signal level going high on an external pin of the chip, but it increasingly applies to internal events as well, such as events generated by smart peripherals on the same chip, or by exception being generated. A typical generic sequence of events on an advanced multi-core chip, such as the Texas Instruments C6678 multi-DSP [TMS320C6678] is as follow:

1. The hardware will often disable all other possible event sources from being passed on to the interrupt controller
2. The external event must be gated through the interrupt controller. Interrupt handling happens often in configurable “layers”. In the case of the Texas Instruments C6678, one can distinguish 3 layers allowing up to 1000 event sources, requiring to go to multiple look-up tables
3. The Interrupt Service Routine (ISR) is entered
4. Essential registers are saved on a stack
5. The ISR specific code is executed
6. The interrupt context is restored
7. Upon exit of the ISR, the interrupted code is resumed or when programmed in the ISR, control is transferred to a local OS kernel

It is clear that several factors influence the latency of reacting to the event:

- hardware design of the interrupt controller;
- number of simultaneous interrupt sources;
- length of the ISR code;
- size of the context Switch (as this requires disabling of interrupts).

The challenge on advanced many/multi-core chips is multiple:

- interrupts can be shared by multiple cores;
- many interrupts are associated with shared on-chip resources;

- memory can be shared requiring caches to be flushed;
- often the interrupt handling code will be more complex because the hardware needs more configuration settings.

3.7.2 Profiling requirements

In order to measure the interrupt latency on a real system, following functionality is needed:

- an event generator (connected to the external event pin of the chip) or an equivalent internal interrupt source (e.g. an on-chip programmable timer);
- a way to measure the time interval between the event and the measured instruction (e.g. reading the value). This needs to be with high precision, typically in clock pulses. A typical set up uses an on-chip high precision timer or an external logic analyser. In the latter case, the measurement is signalled by changing the logical level on an external pin.

3.7.3 Current available solutions

There is no general solution on the market to measure interrupt latency. Each vendor uses its own set-up and often a proprietary definition. For example sometimes interrupt latency is measured as the time interval that interrupts are disabled in the OS kernel code, which is only a contributing factor. Moreover, there is no standardized way to measure the impact of the cache policy. While some processors provide profiling support, such as hardware counters that count cache misses, the results are often difficult to interpret. In addition, on-board hardware that shares the memory bus and/or generates undocumented interrupt events are not uncommon.

4 Profiling methodologies, tools and HW/SW mechanisms

This section provides the description of adopted profiling methodologies, also highlighting preliminary design issues of tools and related HW/SW mechanisms that will be developed/integrated and eventually used to perform profiling actions finally evaluating the defined metrics. For each methodology are provided information about which metrics are evaluated, main design issues (HW and/or SW ones) and general consideration about accuracy and introduced overhead.

4.1 *Hardware performance counters*

Methodologies based on ad-hoc hardware implementations are often adopted in order to avoid possible distortion of system behavior due to the monitoring action, thus satisfying non-intrusive profiling requirement.

4.1.1 UAQ

The use of hardware performance counters has been adopted by UAQ to profile memory and HW communication in order to avoid possible distortion of system behavior due to the monitoring action, thus satisfying non-intrusive profiling requirement. Profiling data are collected by means of proper HW sniffers during software execution and buffered in a local temporary memory unit. At the end of software execution, a monitor unit collects required data in order to communicate them to the central processor or to an external supervisor (e.g. a PC equipped with a profiling data reporting and visualization tool).

4.1.1.1 *Evaluated Metrics*

Implemented mechanisms address the following metrics:

- Memory Exploitation Metrics (sec. 3.1)
- Hardware Communications Metrics (sec. 3.2)

4.1.1.2 *Methodology and design issues*

Proposed architecture includes two main subsystems: event detection subsystem and global system monitor. Event detection subsystem detect and collect selected hardware events and notify them to the global system monitor. Figure 7 shows developed profiling mechanisms general architecture for a basic single core test platform (profiling specific mechanisms are highlighted in blue).

Figure 7 – General architecture of profiling subsystem

In the proposed approach, the event detection subsystem is distributed along the target architecture, while the global monitor unit acts as a global coordinator. Each profiling target element is associated with a dedicated profiling resource. A profiling resource, namely an event detector, is indicated as “sniffer”. Each sniffer is able to monitor a system interconnection (e.g. the memory bus, the communication bus between two processing elements, etc..), collect metric related events and communicate with the global monitor unit. Processor unit communicates with profiling resource over a dedicated bus infrastructure (Log Bus). Profiling results are reported over a second dedicated bus (Profiling Data Bus) to a Monitor Unit. This core has two main function:

- handling of information flow and interrupt signals from sniffer units to central processor;
- interface with external debugger devices for information and trace visualization and reporting.

The separation between Log Bus and Profiling Data Bus avoids conflicts between sniffer setup and configuration actions and measure reporting. This choice, together with the hardware based approach for resource development, ensures light overhead on run time code execution. The monitor module acts as a memory-mapped peripheral for the generic processor unit, communicating on generic system bus.

Each address bus sniffer includes (Figure 8):

- One or more event counters, with each counter specifically configured for a single metric tracing. Each counter will include a local control unit able to track selected event and update a local counter or an optional time-stamping unit
 - Event counter design, and specifically event detection section, must guarantee a high grade of flexibility, in order to not tie down profiling possibility to specifically implemented core architecture.
- A dispatcher, i.e. a global sniffer controller. Main processor is able to configure a set of control register via the dedicate log bus interface. On the basis of control register configuration, the dispatcher will setup and configure specified event counter.
- A local timer, used to track time intervals associated with specific events.

Figure 8 –Schematic architecture of the sniffer unit

Processor communicate with the single sniffer unit over the dedicated log bus. The dispatcher unit includes a custom log bus interface. The processor can address the single counter and enable and disable profiling through start and stop commands. The dispatcher is able to receive processor commands and to activate the right counter signal to start the right counting actions. At the end of selected profiling period, the global monitor unit is able to read the value of each single counter over the dedicated Profiling Data Bus and to report collected data to one or more of the system processor. Optionally, the global monitor unit can send profiling data to an external processing/display unit over a traditional communication interface (for example, a serial line).

The sniffer includes a dedicated timer unit that runs under system main clock. This timer is used to measure elapsed time between two events. The dedicated time-stamping logic of each event counter is used to pick specific time value and associate them to selected events of interest.

Memory profiling follows the general approach of runtime address bus sampling. Prototype design will primarily target Xilinx native bus solution for a Microblaze based processing system (e.g. Xilinx Local Memory Bus, Xilinx Cache Link).

HW Communication profiling is based on a bus transaction sniffer integrated in the general architecture and so, also in this case, on runtime bus sampling. Event detector architecture is revised in order to allow selected communication bus monitoring. The unit is able to detect and measure transaction events occurring on a generic target bus. Preliminary design of communication bus sniffer will target IBM PLB bus; porting to a different bus architecture will require only a revision of the event detector unit.

4.1.1.3 *Generated outputs*

The generated outputs is related to the evaluated metrics. The detailed data format will be defined during the project and reported in next T3.5.1 deliverables.

4.1.1.4 *Profiling accuracy and overhead*

Proposed hardware implementation allows to avoid the introduction of software execution overhead, as all memory statistics are derived by the simple observation of memory address bus data. The occurrence of preliminarily specified address directly triggers the operation of sniffer units, avoiding the introduction of temporal delay for profiling process.

Practical implementation of profiling resources has a cost in terms of additional area occupation needed and energy consumption increase. This cost will be further analyzed and characterized during prototype testing phase.

4.2 *Binary instrumentation*

Binary instrumentation is a procedure which takes as input the application executable, and using various techniques is able to trigger certain actions at specific points of the execution.

4.2.1 **BBT**

Each binary instrumentation framework can offer various instrumentations points and triggers. BBT profiling methodology relies mostly on instrumenting function calls and memory access instructions. One important aspect to take into account when performing binary instrumentation is the overhead both in terms of execution cycles and memory consumption. As the metrics that will be measured can be repetitive during an application lifetime, BBT will consider various methods that will allow the reduction of the overhead compared to the state of the art. These metrics will be collected by QUAD [QUAD_2013] profiling tool which is based on dynamic binary instrumentation framework. In the context of CRAFTERS, QUAD will be redesigned and extended to consider multi-threading aspects and the temporal relations between functions and memory access patterns within functions.

4.2.1.1 *Evaluated metrics*

The metrics that we focus are the following:

- Software Communications Metrics (sec. 3.3)

4.2.1.2 *Methodology and design issues*

The following steps will be performed in order to profile the application using QUAD:

- Obtain the binary of the application for an x86 platform. Having debug information would improve the presentation of the collected data but it is not required
- Instrument the application and execute it. This is performed in one step using PIN tools framework [PIN_2013] (the results of this step are presented in the next section)
- Analyze the resulted metrics either in a graphical format or using automated tools
 - Besides direct usage by the developers, BBT considers using the metrics as input for an expert system that will decide the mapping of the functions and will give hints explaining why other mappings were not possible. This will be an external, independent process from the metrics collection.

There are several design issues that have to be considered, we will list the ones we mention here only the most interesting. The first design issue is choosing the granularity and the organization of data structure to store all the collected information. To obtain the best accuracy a low granularity would be required, but this would increase considerable the memory occupied. BBT plan is to propose an adaptable data structure that depending on the available resources will select a finer or a coarser granularity. Another important design issue is at which points in the execution we activate and, maybe deactivate parts of the processing done online.

4.2.1.3 *Generated outputs*

The output will be an XML file that can be used for further processing. An excerpt of such XML file is:

```
<q2:channel producer="main[L12 -&gt; L16]" consumer="main[L18 -&gt; L21]">
  <q2:UnMA>512</q2:UnMA>
  <q2:Bytes>2040</q2:Bytes>
  <q2:UnDV>512</q2:UnDV>
  <q2:UnMARanges>
    <q2:range lower="134520896" upper="134521407" />
  </q2:UnMARanges>
</q2:channel>
```

One example of data presentation is to make a data communication graph between the functions in the application like in Figure 9.

Figure 9 QUAD data communication between functions

4.2.1.4 Profiling accuracy and overhead

Investigating the possibilities to balance the accuracy and overhead is one of our objectives in the QUAD extension in the CRAFTERS project. Currently our tool can provide complete accuracy, this might come with a too high cost in overhead (between x400 and x900 in execution cycles). While it is possible to restrict the profiling to certain parts of the code, the temporal aspect is not yet taken into account, and could not be previously controlled by the user.

4.3 Timestamped execution and memory writes traces

The main purpose of the timestamped execution and memory writes traces is to acquire data necessary to get an insight of the history of software execution within the project. In fact, a timestamped execution trace shows which instructions have been executed on which core at what time.

4.3.1 RPT

RPT will develop a lean and cost-efficient tracing systems for multi-core platforms. Previous experience from the MERASA project [MERASA_2013] will be applied to collect timed execution traces for execution time measurements. Moreover, RPT will investigate profiling solutions for the *Infineon TriCore* architecture and technology [TRICORE_2013].

A timestamped execution trace shows which instructions have been executed on which core at what time. The trace contains three elements:

- the location of the instruction that has been executed;
- the core on which the instruction is executed;
- the time at which the instruction gets executed.

4.3.1.1 *Evaluated Metrics*

A timestamped execution trace can be used also to evaluate metrics in the following categories:

- Execution Time Metrics (sec. 3.4)
- CPU Load and Status Metrics (sec. 3.5)
- Code Coverage Metrics (sec. 3.6)
- Memory Exploitation Metrics (sec. 3.1)
 - In fact, by exploiting a timestamped execution trace, it is also possible to obtain a timestamped trace of memory write operations

4.3.1.2 *Methodology and design issues*

There are three possible ways of recording location and core:

- Software-based instrumentation (SW) in which software is executed to indicate that specific locations have been executed and the core on which they are executed
- Hardware instruction trace (HI), where each instruction that is executed and the core on which it is executed is recorded through a hardware mechanism
- Hardware branch trace (HT), where each branch that is executed and the core on which it is executed is recorded through a hardware mechanism

There are three possible ways of recording the instruction execution time:

- Software-based reading of a free-running clock (SC)
 - This is compatible with software-based instrumentation only
- External timestamping of trace data that is presented via an external interface (ET)
 - This is compatible with all location/core approaches described above
- Internal timestamping of trace data via on-chip mechanisms (IT)
 - This is compatible with both hardware approaches

This gives us the following possible mechanisms: SW/SC, SW/ET, HI/IT, HI/ET, HT/IT, HT/ET.

Key design issues are then the as following:

- ensuring synchronization between timestamps applied on different cores;
- minimizing run-time overhead of instrumentation (especially if SW instrumentation is required);
- minimizing variability of instrumentation execution times (especially if SW instrumentation is required);

- CPU speeds mean that a large volume of trace data is generated very quickly, so issues of storing and transmitting trace data are significant.

Timestamped trace of memory writes (and also different metrics) could be obtained from a timestamped execution trace using a SW/ET type of instrumentation, where instrumentation point identifiers are written to a specific memory location and timestamped via some external mechanism. In this approach, instrumentation points are placed at relevant locations in the code. The implementation of the instrumentation point depends upon the metric which needs to be collected. The instrumentation point should typically provide some way of determining the current location being executed, and the core on which it is executing. It can also provide additional information for specific metrics, for example:

- cache memory status could be used to see if there are any pathological cache behaviours that always affect a specific piece of code.
- CPU temperature or power consumption

This mechanism necessarily requires some external agent capable of reading and timestamping the specific memory location. This could be implemented by a debugger supporting a protocol like *NEXUS level 3* (<http://nexus5001.org/>), or it could be implemented as a data logger (for example a logic analyzer) monitoring an output port.

4.3.1.3 *Generated outputs*

The output from a timestamped instruction trace is a triple:

```
<location/instrumentation point identifier, core, time>
```

The instruction trace might be held internally on the measured system, or externally.

The output from a timestamped trace of memory writes is a trace of pairs:

```
<value written, timestamp>
```

If multiple memory locations are monitored (for example, one location per core), the trace should also include the memory location from which the value was read.

4.3.1.4 *Profiling accuracy and overhead*

The accuracy of the profiling is affected by the specific approach taken:

- internal timestamping (IT) of the data typically provides the highest accuracy of the trace, as the clock is synchronized with the CPU;
- where timestamps are not synchronized with the CPU, as can be the case with external timestamping (ET), the profiling accuracy is reduced especially when the timestamps are used to measure periods. Measurements of the software clock are usually accurate (as the free-running counter used for this measurement is typically synchronized to the CPU clock). The precision of the measurement will be affected because of the overhead of the software instrumentation.

Overheads for profiling are as follows:

- silicon space required to implement hardware traces (HI or HT)

- program memory required to store additional instructions required for SW instrumentation;
- additional execution time required to execute instructions implementing SW (and possible SC) instrumentation
- possible overhead required to store the trace (if they are not stored externally).

4.3.2 BUT/CAMEA

The main purpose of the timestamped execution and memory writes traces is to acquire data necessary to get an insight of the history of software execution within the project.

4.3.2.1 *Evaluated Metrics*

Implemented mechanisms address the following metrics:

- Execution Time Metrics (sec. 3.4)
- CPU Load and Status Metrics (sec. 3.5)
- Memory Exploitation Metrics (sec. 3.1)
 - In fact, by exploiting a timestamped execution trace, it is also possible to obtain a timestamped trace of memory write operations

4.3.2.2 *Methodology and design issues*

The easiest way is to insert special macros directly into source code. These macros are writing current time with user defined flags into data structure, later written into file or database. For occasional timestamping (program start, error, user input, ...), the real-time clock is the good solution. Obtaining current time is long procedure, so it is not advisable to be used in time-critical or frequently executed parts of code. In this case, obtaining a number of clock cycles after program start is much faster.

Memory write operations can be traced in the same way, i.e. by inserting macros into specific places in program code.

The main design issues are that changing of code by inserting macros can cause some unexpected application behaviour or cause some time-dependent bugs. Problem could rise also with saving the timestamps, because file writing is often blocking operation. Another problem is where to place the profiling macros in order to get relevant results.

4.3.2.3 *Generated outputs*

File or database with timestamps is later processed with specialized software. It has to be able to display program action statistics and time graphs, search within records for specific action, etc... Figure 10 shows a screenshot of CAMEA timestamp processing software, which will be enhanced within CRAFTERS project.

Figure 10 Screenshot of times execution trace tool

The same tool can be used for processing and displaying profiling stamps related to *Memory Exploitation Metrics*.

4.3.2.4 Profiling accuracy and overhead

Proposed solution is accurate, because it is based on inserting timestamp macros directly into source code. Therefore there is no possibility of inaccurate results unlike statistical profiling methods, where program status is passively scanned.

This solution have a small overhead related to timestamp macro content. Usually, profiling macros contains time requests code and function calls for saving timestamps into file/database.

4.4 RTOS Integrated Approaches

HW/SW mechanisms described above to perform profiling are often directly integrated into RTOS. However, these mechanisms usually require a modified kernel, which is used to record traces of a variety of events. But using a modified kernel could lead to differences between the actual production kernel and the profiling kernel, thus making the profiling invalid as soon as high performance is required. In the context of the CRAFTERS project two RTOS are considered and extended, and so briefly described in the following: *Altreonic OpenComRTOS* and *HIPPEROS*.

4.4.1 ALT

Altreonic OpenComRTOS [GW_2013] provides a lot of profiling support that could be used and extended to evaluate a relevant subset of the metrics described in Section 3 (in

particular *ISR and Task Latency Metrics*, sec. 3.7) by exploiting described HW/SW mechanisms. In general, it provides:

- *Event Tracer*
 - Event tracing is achieved by using a modified RTOS kernel with tracing enabled that records essential tracing information in a circular buffer on each processing node in the system.
 - On a host node (e.g. a PC), a command can be generated to dump all traces to files. The files are processed and visually presented in the *OpenTracer* tool with a GUI:
 - event lists show the event and their time stamps;
 - the duration between two events are calculated;
 - a visual display (like on an oscilloscope) is generated;
 - the interactions between the nodes are extracted and displayed;
 - CPU load per task in the traced interval are calculated.
 - The OpenTracer tool provides a linear time as well as logarithmic time display. It also allows to select partial traces to measure execution times between selected events.
- *Open System Inspector*
 - This tool uses a demon task on each processing node that communicates on demand with a GUI tool on a host node. It allows to inspect the use of RTOS kernel resources as well as worst case usage and inspect e.g. memory. Following entities can be inspected:
 - all kernel service hubs (event, semaphores, fifos, resource_locks, memory pools, packet pools, stack usage);
 - communication driver packets.
- *Workload measurements*
 - Using a *modified idle loop*, the application idle time is measured over a user defined interval. This allows to deduct the application workload.
- *Standard set-up for measuring interrupt latencies*
 - A standard set-up is provided to measure interrupt latencies and display the resulting histogram using a GUI tool on a host node. The measurement requires a periodic timer with the capability to read the timer value with a high precision. The hardware timer is used to generate a periodic interrupt whereby two interrupt latencies are defined and measured:
 - IRQ to ISR latency: the generated interrupt calls an ISR in which the timer value is read. The difference between the timer interrupt and the measured time is called the IRQ to ISR latency
 - IRQ to task latency: the ISR passes an event to a waiting task (via the RTOS kernel). The timer value is read again. The interval between the timer interrupt and measured time is called the IRQ to task latency

- To stress test the RTOS, two additional tasks signal each other using semaphores. This generates continuous context switches (whereby interrupts are partly disabled) and can be considered as a worst case load for interrupt handling. The results are collected in real-time on a host node and graphically displayed
 - This mechanism is easily ported to other hardware and (RT)OS configurations. And can also be adapted to use an external logic analyzer, rather than an on-chip timer
- The measurements outlined are repeated for different cache settings (target specific). Typical set-ups are:
 - all caching disabled;
 - L2 enabled, L1 disabled;
 - L1 and L2 enabled;
 - L1 and L2 enabled with periodic flushing of L1 cache.

Note that this approach will provide best case figures as on a real system interrupt latency is application specific. Hence the result is not a single figure but a statistical histogram whereby it is important that:

- the statistical spread is narrow enough;
- the worst-case latencies are strictly bounded (no Poisson distribution but a block-like diagram).

4.4.2 ULB

A variety of systems collect information of processes, resources and platforms. This section is particular for embedded and real-time systems and the following describes the mechanisms of HIPPEROS RTOS, with the assumption that these are representative of what can/should be available in multi-core embedded systems. HIPPEROS provides a lot of profiling support that could be used and extended to evaluate a relevant subset of the metrics described in Section 3.

Profiling for process state changes, viewed from an RTOS, include the tracing of all process current states (Inactive, Unreleased, Ready, Processing, Waiting, Blocked, Completed) and the corresponding state transitions. Information available from the *RTOS Process Manager* include elapsed process time, remaining process time until WCET, deadline, priority, memory, stack and resources used and processor assignment. Metrics based on that information can then be derived, in particular COT (Completion On Time) and QoS (Quality of Service) metrics. Utilities similar to *ps*, *top*, etc can be used by a monitoring service or by an interactive user process.

Profiling of middleware and RTOS overheads such as preemptions and migrations, and other cases of context switches, is available when the RTOS supports them. In the case of HIPPEROS, it is possible to collect metrics such as the number, frequency and duration of the above overheads, as well as the overheads created by the execution of the kernel services themselves.

It is possible to gather statistics in IRQ calls and duration of ISRs, usage of shared resources, usage of IPC, etc. In particular, information is available on latencies for process

events (process to process, preemption, migration), for kernel actions (kernel to process) and interrupt handling (IRQ to ISR, ISR to process).

Profiling of memory and stacks include in particular information on the current and maximum usage of static memory and stack by the user and system processes. In particular, information on cache usage and cache misses can be traced.

Profiling statistics metrics are required in order to profile and optimize the execution of the whole system on a multi-core platform. The profiling of the process statistics to be evaluated include mainly:

- profiling of the process state changes (RTOS view);
- profiling of the process at the semantic level (user view);
- profiling of RTOS overheads such as preemptions and migrations (context switching);
- profiling of IRQ handling and ISRs;
- profiling of communication and synchronization mechanisms;
- profiling of memories and stacks.

In HIPPEROS, mechanisms for supporting profiling are thus available:

- a modified *Hipperos Profiling Kernel* can be used to create event traces (*logs*) for processes, resources and RTOS events (these can then be dumped to a separate system but this is not the preferred approach);
- the *Hipperos Monitor* is an optional kernel module that adds profiling functionality, but which can ideally run on a separate core without impacting the production system (this approach allows for profiling of the productive kernel directly).

The output of the above mechanisms can then be analyzed offline by a variety of tools, e.g. the OMETRIS tool [OMETRIS_2013] made by UEG. Using such a tool, it is possible to analyze the frequency of events, their duration, the handling latencies and other attributes. It is also possible to compare actual executions with simulated executions.

5 IP-XACT standard for abstract platform representation

This section describes a standard notation, IP-XACT (IEEE 1685-2009: IP-XACT), that could be used in the context of the CRAFTERS project to provide a unified view of platform descriptions associated to the metrics described in Section 3 and evaluated by means of the techniques described in Section 4. This unified model could be a reference (maybe together with alternative/complementary models, e.g. MARTE [MARTE_2013]) for several tools of the whole CRAFTERS design flow. In particular, IP-XACT is particularly suited to support design space exploration activities (DSE). For this, the following describes the standard and its relationships with DSE.

5.1 Attributes available in IP-XACT elements

The goal of this section is to describe the main elements available in IP-XACT notation.

5.1.1 Attributes of component

An IP-XACT component (Figure 11) is the central placeholder for the objects meta-data. Components are used to describe cores (processors, co-processors, DSPs, etc.), peripherals (memories, DMA controllers, timers, UART, etc.), and buses (simple buses, multi-layer buses, cross bars, network on chip, etc.). An IP-XACT component can be a hierarchical object or a leaf object. Leaf components do not contain other IP-XACT components, while hierarchical components contain other IP-XACT sub-components. This can be recursive by having hierarchical components that contain hierarchical components, etc. The available attributes are described in the following paragraphs.

Figure 11: IP-XACT Component Overview

Name and version: the so called VLNV (Vendor, Library, Name, Version) gives information of the actual component instantiated in a design. It may be used in conjunction with other documents like data sheet to retrieve the technical performances of the component.

Parameters: Some parameters are used to configure or parameterize the instantiated component. Thus these parameters may be used for the performances reporting, but to do

so, as parameters names are not standardized, it is mandatory to adopt a naming convention between the IP provider and the engine used for design space exploration.

Interfaces: A component may have several Bus Interfaces. Each interface is defined with a name, a reference to a Bus Type (an existing Bus definition) and to an Abstraction Type (an existing Abstraction Definition). The Port Maps allow mapping the ports of the component model with the ports of the logical ports of the Abstraction Definition (see Figure 12). A bus Interface can also have two directions types Master or Slave. The interface is thus containing a lot of structural information to be used by a specific report engine.

Figure 12 Bus Interface Overview

Model: The group Model is used to describe the information related to the model of the component. It specifies all the different *Views* (e.g. level of abstraction, or modeling language, or a power model, etc.), the *Ports*, and the *Model Parameters*. In particular:

- The Views allow to define several views for a same component, for instance several level of abstraction (RTL, TLM, CABA, etc.), or several modeling languages (VHDL, Verilog, SystemC, etc.), etc. Each view has a File Set Ref. List which allows specifying one or more File Sets that are available to use the component model.
- The Ports are the list of ports for the considered component. A port is an external connection from the object. An object may only have one set of ports that shall be valid for all views.
- The Model Parameters contain a list of parameters that are needed to configure a model implementation specified in a view. An object shall only have one set of model parameters that are valid for all views (constructor parameters, generics, etc.).
- File Sets: An important part of the schema is dedicated to referencing the files related to the different views of a component: a view may be for instance a simulable model in a specific language (VHDL, Verilog, SystemC, etc.) or documentation files (e.g. PDF, HTML, Framemaker). This work facilitates future reuse of existing components, because all of their features are easily accessible for its integration and configuration in a bigger system, which consist the second step of the flow.

- Each Memory Map is composed of Address Blocks, defined by a name, a Width, a Base Address, a Range and some other attributes. One can also add additional parameters. In general, it specifies the addressable area as seen from bus interfaces with an interface mode of slave.

So, all these attributes also gives structural information, parameters information, etc. It is a very important category to consider for reporting.

Channel or Bridge: An IP-XACT component may contain a channel or a bridge. A channel is a special IP-XACT object that can be used to describe multi-point connections between regular components that may require some interface adaptation. A bridge is a point-to-point reference of slave to master interfaces. Both of these concepts are used to describe the interconnect between components

5.1.2 Interface Definition Description

A *Bus Definition* is identified with a VLNV. It may have several implementations using Abstraction Definitions (see Figure 13a).

An *Abstraction Definition* is identified with a VLNV. Each Abstraction Definition allows defining several implementations of a same *Bus Definition*. Indeed, designs that incorporate IP models using different interface modeling styles (e.g., TLM and RTL modeling styles) may contain interconnections between such component interfaces using different abstractions of the same bus type. An abstraction definition allows defining the ports (identified with a *Logical Name*) that are available in the bus interface; these ports may be for example typed *Wire* (for RTL ports) or *Transactional* (for TLM ports).

An *Abstractor* is a special-purpose object of a design configuration. It is used to describe how interconnections are to be made to connect between two different abstractions of the same bus type (e.g., an APB_RTL and an APB_TLM). An abstractor shall only contain two interfaces, which shall be of the same bus definition and different abstraction definitions (see Figure 13b).

Figure 13 Interface Description Properties

The *directConnection* element is defined in a Bus Definition. It specifies what connections are allowed. The *directConnection* element is of type *Boolean* for which a value of true specifies these interfaces may be connected in a direct master to slave fashion. A value of false indicates only non-mirror to mirror type connections are allowed (i.e., master-mirroredMaster, slave-mirroredSlave, or system-mirroredSystem) (see Figure 14).

Figure 14 Connection Direction

5.1.3 Design Description

A *Design* is identified with a VLNV. A Design is an assembly of *Components Instances* connected with *AdHoc Connections* (port to port) and *Inter Connections* (between interfaces). Figure 15 is a representation of a design by Magillem tools. A hierarchical component has a view which is not referencing a FileSet but a Design using its VLNV.

Figure 15 Design Overview using Magillem Tool

An IP-XACT Design can be composed of the following elements:

Component instances with parameter configuration: Each Component Instance references a Component using its VLNV identifier and has an Instance Name.

Adhoc connections: are port slice to port slice connections. Each AdHoc Connection is identified with a name and lists *Internal Port References* specified with the name of an Instance and the connected port. Thus all ports referenced in this list are connected together with a wire. Connections are from several type (between instances, between instances and the top interface, can be used to tie ports to a certain value, busInterface connections, etc.) and shall be processed differently by a report engine.

5.2 Extensions of IP-XACT for Context labels

Because IP-XACT is intended to only capture fixed facts about an IP and avoid capturing functional information, context labels are proposed to enrich the IP-XACT elements description. Context labels are defined for components and for their interfaces (i.e. individual ports and/or buses). When the hierarchy of an IP-XACT design is traversed, the constituting components are inspected for context labels. These context labels are attached to the components themselves, to bus interfaces or to individual ports. They can be overruled by similar context labels in a design file where they are attached to component instances, interconnections and ad-hoc interconnections, respectively. These

context labels are formally defined and constitute a SPRINT [SPRINT_2013] proposal to enhance the SPIRIT IP-XACT 1.4 standard (www.accellera.org) to contain behavioral properties of an IP component or interface. The following tables define these labels for components and interfaces

5.2.1 Component Labels

Contemporary SoC designs consist of IP cores like interconnection network, processors, peripheral cores, etc. Such core-based designs contain design IPs that belongs to one of the main IP groups which have been listed in label definitions. Examples of context labels are <isNetwork-Component> for bridges, busses etc.; <isInfrastructureComponent> for Clk and Reset generators, Interrupt Controllers etc. The following table lists components labels.

Components Labels	Elements
isNetworkComponent	Bridges, tunnels, adapters, buses...
isConnectivityComponent	Off-chip interface : UART,USB,I2C,GPIO
isStreamingComponent	Video data processor, ...
isInfrastructureComponent	Clock and reset generator, interrupt controller
isProcessorComponent	CPU, DSP, ARM, MIPS, TriMedia, ...
isInternalComponent	Peripheral without off-chip interface, e.g. mem.
isTestControlComponent	Dedicated Dft component
isSubComponent	Testbench component connected to off-chip interface
isVerificationComponent	Verification monitor, or testbench component
isUndefindeComponent	To capture all other components

Table 1 Components Labels Definition

There are also Infrastructure component sub-labels for elements such as clock generators, reset generators, interrupt controllers, configuration registers etc.

5.2.2 Interface Labels

The interface labels are tags showing the intended use (design intent) of a bus interface or port. A system designer may have a different use for an IP interface; this should then be annotated to the IP instance in the system design.

Interface Labels	Elements
IsNetworkInterface	MMIO slave bus interface
isConnectivityInterface	Off-chip interface
isStreamingInterface	Direct IP-to-IP interface

isInfrastructureInterface	Interface to infrastructure IP
isTestWrapperInterface	DfT interface; not software-accessible
isUndefinedInterface	To capture all other interfaces

Table 2 Interface Labels Definition

There are also Connectivity interface sub-labels and Infrastructure interface sub-labels for elements such as clock inputs, reset inputs interrupt request input DMA flow control interface etc...

5.3 Extract information from IP-XACT for design space exploration

The main goal of design space exploration is to estimate several types of performances of a system; this system is composed of an application software running on a hardware platform; in MultiSoC the targeted platform may be an assembly of several IPs or several sub-systems, considered through a large variability of parameters. Considering all possibilities in the choice of the target hardware platform, the challenges of design space exploration are the following:

- capability to build automatically the several candidate platforms following the specification of explored configurations;
- mapping the application;
- reporting of performances.

For all these challenges, IP-XACT standard has no competitor and is now used widely in the industry and research area. The goal is to use static information contained in IP-XACT documentation to bring report of performances useful for design space exploration. In fact, IP-XACT may be used to describe a platform at several levels of abstraction: roughly we can split have three levels: high level (specification), transactional level (TLM prototype), RTL (accurate description).

The goal in design space exploration is to use an existing version of one of these levels to produce a abstracted representation of the platform that is exploitable for the performance analysis.

An abstract platform is determined by considering the platform characteristics that are relevant for applications at a certain level of platform-independence as well as the various design goals. We identify three levels of abstraction models:

- The structural description level
- The communication description level
- The functional description level

5.3.1 Structural Description Level

The structural description level provides the following information:

- Components Description
- Components Interface Types
- Interconnections between components

These elements can be provided by the IP-XACT description of the platform. Component labels allow the identification of components and interconnections types. On this layer, several architecture building blocks are available that can be used to assemble the system architecture. These building blocks can be of type software processors, memories or user-defined hardware. The blocks can be connected via busses or point-to-point connections. Given a formal definition of the platform description level, we will be able to automatically generate the elements constituting the model.

5.3.2 Communication Description Level

The communication description level addresses the notion of communication between IP components of a given platform. Indeed, this description layer is essential when it comes to mapping an application layer to a target architecture layer of the platform. It involves the mapping of modules and shared objects of appropriate architecture building blocks. Besides the mapping of modules and Shared Objects the logical communication links in the application layer model have to be mapped on physical communication resources in the target architecture model of the platform. In this refinement process, multiple communication links can either be bundled in a physical shared bus or each communication link can be mapped to a dedicated point-to-point connection. A communication description layer becomes essential.

In this purpose we need to analyze the connection types in the IP-XACT description of the platform and the way they are structured.

5.3.3 Functional Description Level

The functional description level gives an abstract model of the platform for service-oriented development. Thus, we are addressing the functional aspects of the platform. The description should include information such as:

- the services provided by the platform;
- the performances of the platform.

This level of abstraction is linked to data processing of a given platform. This may include power consumption features, computation performances, identification within the platform how much processors are available and their specifications. We may need to know the type of provided memory, their size, etc. We will need information such as components types: CPU, memory, communication element. We may also need to get additional information from other specification files.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable, together with related D5.3 and D5.9, represents the main output of task T3.5.1. The task describe, develop and deliver *profiling techniques* (i.e. methodologies, metrics, tools and related HW/SW mechanisms) to monitor computational behavior and communication patterns of hardware/software components of many-CPU/many-core systems representing the CRAFTERS platform. The main goal is to collect data from such systems and made them available for offline analysis and visualization or online use. Moreover, for safety critical systems, they could be used to enforce timing encapsulation and potentially provide recovery mechanisms to improve system availability under the influence of hard or soft errors and for coverage of some systemic software problems. So, this deliverable has provided the first results of task T3.5.1 while describing platforms, metrics, and preliminary integration/design activities of tools and HW/SW mechanisms to be used to monitor computational behavior and communication patterns of hardware/software components. In particular, it has focused on metrics at component-level grain while the following T3.5.1 deliverables will focus on platform-level and system-level issues also providing working prototypes and a final demo.

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